

Giffonins as contributors to the bitter off-taste in hazelnuts

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Abstract

Hazelnuts are important raw materials for the bakery and confectionary industry, due to their highly appreciated nutty, roasted, cocoa and buttery taste profile. However, in recent years an intensive, long lasting bitter off-taste of hazelnuts was reported. Cyclic diarylheptanoid natural products were identified as putative inducers of this bitter off-taste. In order to get a deeper knowledge about the natural products that are responsible for this bitter off-taste, the access to such compounds via isolation from ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnuts or total synthesis was investigated. The key steps of the synthesis include ALDOL-reaction to construct the heptanoid-chain and a metal-assisted coupling to close the 13-membered ring.

Keywords: diarylheptanoid, hazelnut, bitter off-taste

Introduction

The taste of raw hazelnuts is described as nutty, oily, fruity, sweet and caramel-like with a lasting desirable after taste, whereas roasted hazelnuts are dominated by a roasted and coffee-like aroma. However, in the last years a bitter off-taste in hazelnuts has been reported. This off-taste is still detectable after roasting and therefore also noticeable in finished products leading to consumer complaints and economic losses for the food industry. Activity-guided fractionation and taste dilution analysis of hazelnut kernel (*Corylus avellana L.*) extracts led to the identification of cyclic diarylheptanoid natural products, as putative inducers of this bitter off-taste [1]. Amongst others, Giffonin O (3) was identified as one of the candidates for this taste defect. Since 2015 different diarylheptanoids (Giffonins A-V, Carpinontriol B (5)) were isolated from the leaves, flowers and shells of hazelnuts [2] (Table 1). For most of them no sensory properties are known.

Table 1: Diarylheptanoids isolated from the leaves, flowers and shells of hazelnuts.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅
Giffonin L (1)	OH	H	OH	OH	OH
Giffonin M (2)	OH	H	OH	=O	H
Giffonin O (3)	OH	OH	=O	H	OH
Giffonin P (4)	OH	OH	OH	OH	OH
Carpinontriol B (5)	OH	OH	OH	=O	H

In order to get a deeper knowledge about sensory properties of these cyclic diarylheptanoids, the access to such compounds is highly relevant, as larger amounts of reference samples would be needed to explore effective masking solutions for mitigating these taste defects.

Within this study the isolation of cyclic diarylheptanoids from ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnuts was accomplished. In addition we focussed on the development of a synthetic strategy towards these natural products. The key steps of the synthesis include an ALDOL-reaction to construct the heptanoid-chain followed by a metal-assisted coupling to close the 13-membered ring.

Experimental

The ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnuts were selected from the hazelnut harvest of 2017 in Italy. The solvents and chemicals for the synthesis were purchased from HONEYWELL, SIGMA ALDRICH or ALFA AESER.

The measured NMR data of the isolated cyclic diarylheptanoid natural products matched the published data [2, 3].

Preparation of the ketone **20**: *n*-BuLi (0.13 mL, 0.33 mmol, 2.5 M solution in THF) was added dropwise to a solution of anhydrous *i*-Pr₂NH (50 µL, 0.33 mmol) in Et₂O (10.0 mL) at -20 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The

mixture was stirred for 20 min at -20 °C and then cooled to -78 °C. Then, the solution of ketone **18** (100 mg, 0.22 mmol) in Et₂O (3 mL) was added dropwise and the resulting solution was stirred for 30 min at -78 °C. Subsequently, the solution of aldehyde **19** (66 mg, 0.44 mmol) in Et₂O (1 mL) was added dropwise and the resulting solution was stirred for 90 min at -78 °C. The reaction was terminated by the addition of saturated NH₄Cl (25 mL) and vigorously stirred at room temperature (rt) for 10 min. The product was extracted with Et₂O. The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The resulting crude material was purified by column chromatography on silica (hexane/EtOAc = 4:1) to give 105 mg (0.17 mmol) of ketone **20**. Yield: 79 %. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, C₆D₆) δ -0.2 (s, 3H), -0.07 (s, 3H), -0.03 (s, 3H), 0.16 (s, 3H), 0.86 (s, 9H), 0.99 (s, 9H), 2.71 (dd, *J* = 18.65, 9.28 Hz, 1H), 2.72 (dd, *J* = 13.53, 7.24 Hz, 1H), 2.82 (dd, *J* = 13.53, 6.06 Hz, 1H), 2.88 (dd, *J* = 18.25, 2.71 Hz, 1H), 2.95 (dd, *J* = 13.48, 6.14 Hz, 1H), 3.02 (dd, *J* = 13.53, 8.65 Hz, 1H), 3.32 (s, 3H), 3.34 (s, 3H), 4.13 (d, *J* = 1.75 Hz, 1H), 4.23 (ddd, *J* = 8.25, 6.24, 1.75 Hz, 1H), 4.35-4.45 (m, 1H), 6.72-6.82 (m, 4H), 7.02-7.12 (m, 2H), 7.14-7.24 (n, 2H); ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, C₆D₆) δ 214.04 (C), 159.07 (C), 158.90 (C), 131.37 (CH), 130.88 (CH), 130.58 (C), 130.11 (C), 114.26 (CH), 81.24 (CH), 79.36 (CH), 69.05 (CH), 54.81 (CH₃), 54.76 (CH₃), 46.00 (CH₂), 42.80 (CH₂), 39.51 (CH₂), 26.28 (CH₃), 26.02 (CH₃), 18.43 (C), 18.34 (C), -4.12 (CH₃), -4.58 (CH₃), -4.88 (CH₃), -5.31 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI) *m/z* for C₃₃H₅₄O₆Si₂Na [M+Na]⁺ calc. 625.3351, found 625.3352.

Preparation of the ketone **21**: TBSOTf (60 μL, 0.25 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of ketone **20** (100 mg, 0.17 mmol) and 2,6-lutidine (50 μL, 0.42 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (20 mL) at 0 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0 °C and for 1 h at rt. The reaction was terminated by the addition of saturated NaHCO₃ (25 mL) and vigorously stirred at room temperature for 10 min. The product was extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The resulting crude material was purified by column chromatography on silica (hexane/EtOAc = 10:1) to give 110 mg (0.15 mmol) of TBS protected ketone. To the solution of this intermediate (50 mg, 0.07 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL) silver trifluoroacetate (46 mg, 0.21 mmol) was added. Subsequently, a solution of I₂ (53 mg, 0.21 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL) was added dropwise and the resulting suspension was stirred for 30 min at rt. The yellow suspension was filtered through Celite and the filtrate was concentrated. The resulting crude material was purified by column chromatography on silica (hexane/EtOAc = 10:1) to give 50 mg (0.05 mmol) of ketone **21**. Yield: 75 %. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.61 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.58 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.13 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.12 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 6.72 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 4.30 (p, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 4.03 (td, *J* = 7.0, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 3.92 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 3.84 (s, 6H), 2.79 (dd, *J* = 19.1, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.68 (dd, *J* = 19.0, 5.7 Hz, 1H), 2.69 - 2.63 (m, 2H), 2.60 (dd, *J* = 13.6, 4.9 Hz, 1H), 2.58 (dd, *J* = 13.6, 4.9 Hz, 1H), 0.87 (s, 9H), 0.85 (s, 9H), 0.83 (s, 9H), 0.01 (s, 3H), 0.01 (s, 3H), -0.01 (s, 3H), -0.09 (s, 3H), -0.12 (s, 3H), -0.21 (s, 3H). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 211.24 (C), 156.76 (C), 156.72 (C), 140.63 (CH), 140.60 (CH), 133.18 (C), 132.71 (C), 131.10 (CH), 130.74 (CH), 110.67 (CH), 85.72 (C), 85.63 (C), 81.52 (CH), 77.70 (CH), 68.67 (CH), 56.42 (CH₃), 47.20 (CH₂), 42.58 (CH₂), 37.96 (CH₂), 26.07 (CH₃), 25.90 (CH₃), 25.88 (CH₃), 18.25 (C), 18.16 (C), 17.99 (C), -4.33 (CH₃), -4.38 (CH₃), -4.70 (CH₃), -4.92 (CH₃), -5.22 (CH₃), -5.24 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI) *m/z* for C₃₉H₆₆I₂O₆Si₃Na [M+Na]⁺ calc. 991.2149, found 991.2152.

Results and discussion

Isolation of diarylheptanoids from hazelnuts

The analysis of the methanol extracts of ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnuts identified several diarylheptanoids. Due to very small concentrations of these natural products only three diarylheptanoids could be isolated and characterised by NMR: giffonin P (**4**), carpinontriol B (**5**) and betulatetraol (**6**) (Figure 1). As the main diarylheptanoid carpinontriol B (**5**) was isolated. The concentration of this compound in ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnut paste was determined to be 136 ppm.

Figure 1: Diarylheptanoids isolated from ‘cimiciato’-defected hazelnut.

The sensory evaluation of carpinontriol B (**5**) confirmed the bitter off-taste (25 ppm solution is equally bitter to a 250 ppm solution of salicin). The other two natural products could be obtained only in very small amounts (concentration in hazelnut paste < 1 ppm), which were not sufficient for the sensory evaluation.

Synthetic strategy towards diarylheptanoid natural products

In order to get access to other diarylheptanoids a variable synthetic strategy was developed. For example, Giffonin O (**3**) was dissected retro synthetically into three fragments: the western fragment (in green), the eastern fragment (in red) and the southern fragment (in blue). A metal-assisted biaryl-coupling is intended to be the key step to close the 13-membered macrocycle. The precursor for this cyclization is envisaged to be prepared by an aldol reaction between the eastern fragment **8** and the coupling product of the western fragment **9** and southern fragment **10** (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Retrosynthesis of Giffonin O (**3**).

The starting point for the synthesis was the preparation of the southern fragment **10** from ethyl pyruvate (**11**). After the protection of the ketone functionality of **11** with ethylene glycol under acidic conditions, the corresponding Weinreb amide **13** was generated. The formation of Weinreb amide was necessary for the GRIGNARD addition to obtain ketone **10**, since the direct alkylation of ester **11** provided mainly the double alkylated product (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Synthesis of the southern fragment. Reaction conditions: a) 1,2-Ethanediol, TFA, PTSA, toluene, reflux, 5 h, 29 %; b) *n*-BuLi, MeNHOMe · HCl, THF, -78 °C, 12 h, 42 %; c) VinylMgBr, THF, -78 °C, 3.5 h, 85 %.

Ruthenium catalysed cross-metathesis between the southern fragment **10** and the western fragment **14** yielded the corresponding ketone **15** in very good yield. To avoid the dimerization of the fragments, the commercially available western fragment **14** was used in excess. By using three equivalents of 4-methoxy-styrene (**14**) full conversion of the southern fragment **10** could be achieved. The resulting α,β -unsaturated ketone **15** was then transferred to the epoxide **16** via 1,4-hydride addition using WILKINSON procedure [4], followed by epoxidation of the resulting enol ether with *m*-CPBA. Subsequent reductive opening of the epoxide with diisobutylaluminum hydride provided the TES-protected diol **17**. During the FeCl₃ catalysed deprotection of the ketone functionality, the TES-protecting group was also cleaved. In the next step the hydroxyl functions were again protected with TBS to obtain the ketone **18**. The following aldol reaction with *para*-methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde (**19**) provided the open chain diarylheptanoid (**20**) in 79 % yield (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Coupling of the fragments. Reaction conditions: a) Hoveyda-Grubbs 2nd gen., CH₂Cl₂, 40 °C, 10 h, 99 %; b) Et₃SiH, RhCl(PPh₃)₃, toluene, 65 °C, 5 h, 95 %; c) *m*-CPBA, NaHCO₃, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C, 4 h, 78 %; d) DIBAL-H, CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C, 6 h, 43 %; e) FeCl₃·6H₂O, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C, 2 h, rt, 1 h, 66 %; f) TBSOTf, 2,6-Lutidine, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 2 h, 80 %; g) (*i*-Pr)₂NH, *n*-BuLi, **19**, -78 °C, Et₂O, 2 h, 79 %.

The TBS-protection, followed by iodination using silver trifluoroacetate and iodine gave the open chain intermediate **21** which was then used as substrate for the metal-assisted macrocyclisation. Macrocyclisation of highly functionalized and rigid precursors is challenging and the conversion of such macrocyclisations is usually poor. Palladium catalysed SUZUKI-coupling was not effective for the desired transformation. The successful formation of the protected Giffonin O (**22**) could be achieved using activated copper or Ni(PPh₃)₄ (Figure 5). However, only small amounts of the desired macrocycle **22** could be isolated. In order to proceed with the synthesis the macrocyclisation has to be optimized further.

Figure 5: Final cyclisation. Reaction conditions: a) TBSOTf, 2,6-Lutidine, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 2 h, 92 %; b) CF₃COOAg, I₂, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 0.5h, 75 %; c) Cu, DEF, 150-180 °C, 4 h; d) Ni(PPh₃)₄, DEF, 110-150 °C, 30 h.

Conclusion

Three cyclic diarylheptanoids from 'cimiciato'-defected hazelnuts were isolated and characterised. The sensory evaluation of carpinontriol B (**5**) confirmed the bitter off-taste. In addition, the synthetic strategy towards the protected Giffonin O (**22**) could be developed. The removal of all remaining protection groups should lead to the target molecule **3**. In addition, the reduction of the ketone and subsequent deprotection should furnish the second diarylheptanoid Giffonin L (**1**) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Final deprotection.

This variable synthetic strategy should also allow the synthesis of further diarylheptanoid natural products with different substitution pattern. In addition, the stereoselective epoxidation of compound **15** should provide access to enantiomerically pure diarylheptanoids.

The sensory evaluation of the diarylheptanoids could provide valuable information about structure activity relationships of the cyclic diarylheptanoids as contributors to the bitter off-taste in hazelnuts. This is highly relevant to explore effective masking solutions for these taste defects.

References

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